

EVALUATION OF FORKI ATHLETE ACHIEVEMENT COACHING PROGRAM IN SOLOK CITY: CIPPO-BASED RESEARCH

Ranti Rahayu ¹, Bafirman ², Gusril ³, Anggun Permata Sari ^{4*},
Japhet Ndayisenga ⁵, Fidès Bangurambona ⁶ and Randi Kurniawan ⁷

^{1,2,3,4,7} Department of Health and Recreation, Faculty of Sports Science,
Universitas Negeri Padang, Indonesia.

^{5,6} Departement of Physical Education and Sport, University of Burundi, Burundi.

*Corresponding Author Email: anggunpermata@fik.unp.ac.id

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11634563](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11634563)

Abstract

Based on the results of observations and interviews with FORKI Solok City coaches, it was stated that the development of Karate sports in Solok City was in a category that was not good compared to other regions. The study aims to evaluate the achievement coaching program for FORKI Solok City athletes using the CIPPO (Context, Input, Process, Product, and Outcome) approach. Data was collected using observation, interviews, documentation, and questionnaires regarding the evaluation of the development of karate sports at FORKI Solok. The data was analyzed using validity and CIPPO tests. The results of this study report that the context component of the standard score is positively directed around 66.67%, input 46.67%, process 33.33%, and product 46.47% with the highest score is 76.67, the score located in the middle is 80.00, the score deviation with an average of 3.40, and the score variation is 11.54. So the effectiveness of the implementation of the FORKI Solok City athlete achievement coaching program from all components, namely context, input, process, and product is classified as quadrant III, which is less effective (+--+), this finding is important to be observed, informing the coaching of athletes' achievements in FORKI or an institution that oversees sports so that a program evaluation is needed.

Keywords: Program Evaluation, Achievement Development, Karate, CIPPO.

INTRODUCTION

The dynamic development of the world makes sports have a variety of new sports that follow the development of the world (Bar-Eli et al., 2024; Oulevey et al., 2024; Zainal Abidin et al., 2023). Many sports actually already have a place in the hearts of the people (Sari, Bafirman, et al., 2023; Sari, Kurniawan, et al., 2023).

One of these sports is the martial arts sport of Karate. Karate sports need to be fostered and increased in achievement because karate sports are one of the sports that are favored by the community (Sari, Kurniawan, et al., 2023; Selviani et al., 2024).

Karate is one of the martial arts sports originating from Japan (di Fronso et al., 2024) Based on the results of observations and interviews with FORKI City coaches, it is stated that the development of Karate sports in Solok City is in a category that is less good than other regions, this statement also refers to updated data when Solok City participated in the last championship, namely Karate Open Mayor Cup Serambi Madinah Solok City.

In this championship, Solok City occupied the 40 th position out of 65 other regions or other dojos that participated in the championship. With the results of the championship, it shows that Karate achievements in Solok City are far behind compared to Karate achievements in other regions.

Karate coaching in Solok City is the first step to continue the goal of achieving talented athletes. This karate coaching is not only supported by the organization concerned, but also requires a strong coach. In an effort to improve achievement in Karate sports in Solok City, it is necessary to evaluate regularly and programmatically (Indika et al., 2023; Sari, Bafirman, et al., 2023).

Evaluation is carried out to determine the achievement of the coaching program and provide recommendations for the next training coaching program (Brooke et al., 2020; Coleman & Eys, 2024; DeMartini et al., 2022; Tabaie et al., 2022).

Sports achievement is determined by the programs that have been prepared by the coach, adequate infrastructure, supporting funding and environmental participation, community, and parental support (Kuchar et al., 2023; Middleton et al., 2020; Noh et al., 2024).

Coaching management also plays an important role so that it can become a totality and commitment in systematic and supportive coaching (Fogaça et al., 2024; Tinoco et al., 2023; Yi et al., 2024). Achievement sports coaching is carried out with the aim of achieving the best possible achievements, so as to advance all sports in Indonesia.

Evaluation of achievement coaching using the CIPPO model is considered capable of evaluating thoroughly. By conducting this research, the aim is to explain how the evaluation of the achievement coaching program for FORKI Solok City athletes using the CIPPO approach, as well as the extent of the effectiveness of the implementation of the achievement coaching program. The importance of this is the basis for researchers to carry out this research.

METHODS

Study Design

This research is an evaluation research, by collecting data, presenting accurate and objective information that occurs in the field regarding the achievement coaching program. This research uses the CIPPO model design by applying and involving all parties in the evaluation starting from context, input, process, product and outcome.

Context discusses the coaching environment, Input is a strategy and program design, which relates to sportsmen / athletes, coaches, facilities and infrastructure, financing. Process is the implementation / application of the performance of the manager / management of the central board of sportsmen / athletes, training activities or processes, facilities and infrastructure and financing.

Product is the achievement of the FORKI Karate coaching program. Outcome is the impact of the coaching results. The following is the design of the CIPPO model that researchers designed in the implementation of the evaluation shown in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1: CIPPO Model Design for the Implementation of Evaluation of Karate Achievement Sports Coaching FORKI Solok City

Participants

A total of 15 male students participated in this study, who were recruited randomly. These participants were athletes, coaches and administrators of FORKI. Participants have stated to comply with the rules and participate voluntarily through a written agreement. Participants were 19.07 ± 0.73 years old, body weight 53 ± 2.16 kg, height 161 ± 6.79 cm, and BMI 21.21 ± 2.07 .

Procedure

Research Development

Data collection in this study was organized based on the following steps: 1) a grid is prepared based on indicators and sub-indicators, and 2) statements are prepared based on the existing grid. Validation according to the concept can be carried out in such a way because of the composition of each statement item. The preparation of the instrument framework is carried out as follows: 1) conducting an assessment, 2) compiling dimensions and indicators, 3) compiling instrument grids, 4) compiling question items, 5) testing the validity (validity, validity, accuracy) and reliability of data, 6) conducting expert judgment, namely assessment by experts related to the substance of the instrument, 7) capturing data using instruments, and 8) data analysis.

Research Instruments

This research instrument is carried out using closed and open instrument patterns. The conception of closed instruments is used through the utilization of instruments in the form of questionnaires or questionnaires. The conception of open instruments is used through the use of instruments, observation, and documentation, and uses questionnaires and sheets as in table 1.

Table 1: Evaluasi metode CIPPO

No	Component	Indicator	Data Source	Data Collection	Data Analysis
1	<i>Context</i>	1. Purpose and foundation of the coaching program.	1. Management of FORKI Solok City	1. Interview 2. Observation 3. Documentation 4. Questionnaire	Description
2	<i>Input</i>	1. Purpose and foundation of the coaching program. Athlete 2. Management 3. Financing 4. Facilities and Infrastructure	1. Purpose and foundation of the coaching program. Coach 2. FORKI Solok City Management 3. Athletes	1. Interview 2. Observation 3. Documentation 4. Questionnaire	Description
3	<i>Procces</i>	1. Purpose and foundation of the coaching program. Athlete 2. Management 3. Financing 4. Facilities and Infrastructure	1. Purpose and foundation of the coaching program. Coach 2. FORKI Solok City Management 3. Athletes	1. Interview 2. Observation 3. Documentation 4. Questionnaire	Description
4	<i>Product</i>	1. Purpose and foundation of the coaching program. Athlete 2. Management 3. Financing 4. Facilities and Infrastructure	1. Purpose and foundation of the coaching program. Coach 2. FORKI Solok City Management 3. Athletes	1. Interview 2. Observation 3. Documentation 4. Questionnaire	Description
5	<i>Outcome</i>	1. Prestasi Atlet	1. Purpose and foundation of the coaching program. Coach 2. FORKI Solok City Management 3. Athletes	1. Interview 2. Observation 3. Documentation 4. Questionnaire	Description

Data Analysis

Descriptive analysis was used to characterize the data of each treatment group. While the validity test was carried out by correlating the score of each item with the total score using the Pearson Product Moment formula. Then, the effectiveness of the program can be analyzed with the CIPPO model with a quantitative approach using the Glickman quadrant. The AHP hierarchy model is weighted on a pairwise comparison matrix at each level.

RESULT

The results of the study in the form of data on components collected through a questionnaire consisting of 88 statement items with 15 respondents filled in by athletes, administrators and coaches of FORKI Solok City. The overall research results seen based on the achievements of respondents, the tendency of evaluating the achievement coaching program for karate athletes FORKI Solok City is classified as less appropriate.

Data analysis can be explained by the results of 8 respondents (53.33%) classified as less appropriate, 5 respondents (33.33%) classified as appropriate, 2 respondents (13.33%) classified as very appropriate, with the following figure 2:

Figure 2: Respondents' Achievement Level in Evaluating the Achievement Development Program of Karate Athletes FORKI Solok City

Quantitatively, based on the level of achievement of respondents from the context indicator FORKI Solok City, the tendency of the context level is classified as appropriate. Based on the results of data analysis, it can be explained: 8 respondents (53.33%) were classified as appropriate, 5 respondents (33.33%) were less appropriate, 2 respondents (13.33%) were classified as very appropriate.

Based on the level of achievement of respondents from the input indicator, the tendency of the suitability level is classified as less suitable. From the results of data analysis can be explained: 7 respondents (46.67%) classified as less suitable, 4 respondents (26.67%) classified as suitable, 3 respondents (20.00%) classified as very suitable, and 1 respondent (6.6667%) classified as not suitable.

Based on the level of achievement of respondents from the process indicator, the tendency of the suitability level is classified as less suitable. From the results of data analysis can be explained: 9 respondents (60.00%) are classified as less suitable, 4 respondents (26.67%) are classified as suitable, 1 respondent (6.67%) is classified as very suitable, and 1 respondent (6.66667%) is classified as not suitable.

Based on the level of achievement of respondents from the FORKI Solok City product indicator, the tendency of the suitability level is classified as less suitable. From the results of data analysis can be explained: 6 respondents (40.00%) classified as less suitable, 4 respondents (26.67%) classified as suitable, 3 respondents (20.00%) classified as very suitable, and 2 respondents (13.3333%) classified as not suitable. The results of each indicator in FORKI Solok City can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Respondents' level of achievement of each indicator

Table 2: Effectiveness of Context, Input, Process and Product Variables

Component	Category Score		Result	Description
	F+	F-		
Context	10	5	+	Positive (+)
Input	7	8	-	Negatif (-)
Process	5	10	-	Negatif (-)
Product	7	8	-	Negatif (-)

Table 3: Persentase Efektivitas Pelaksanaan Program Pembinaan Prestasi Atlet FORKI Kota Solok

Component	% Frequency		%F+ minus %F-	Category Tendency	Category Less
	F+	F-			
Context	66.67	33.33	33.33	+	effective quadrant
Input	46.67	53.33	-6.67	-	
Process	33.33	66.67	-33.33	-	
Product	46.67	53.33	-6.67	+	

In tables 2 and 3, the effectiveness assessment based on the data above if transformed into the Glickman model, it can be concluded that (1) the effectiveness of the implementation of the athlete achievement coaching program FORKI Solok City in terms of context is classified as effective (positive 33.33%); (2) the effectiveness of the implementation of the athlete achievement coaching program FORKI Solok City in terms of input (input) is classified as less effective (negative 6. 67%); (3) the effectiveness of the implementation of the athlete achievement coaching program FORKI Solok City in terms of implementation (process) is classified as less effective (negative 33.33%); (4) the effectiveness of the implementation of the karate athlete achievement coaching program FORKI Solok City in terms of results (product) is classified as effective (positive 67%); so that the effectiveness of the implementation of the athlete achievement coaching program FORKI Solok City from all components, namely context, input, process and product is classified as quadrant III, which is less effective (+--+).

DISCUSSION

The context component in this study contains an analysis of the strengths and weaknesses in running the program. The facilities and infrastructure used by FORKI Solok City are still categorized as lacking, seen from the training building or hall which is used alternately with other sports. Training support equipment such as mats used for training also initially alternated with floor gymnastics branches and also with mats that had begun to be slippery and not very good for use because it could cause athletes to slip during training (Hegyí et al., 2022; Quinzi et al., 2018; Vences Brito et al., 2011; Witte et al., 2016). At night training when preparing for the championship also in the hall where practicing is dark or lack of lighting (Raquel et al., 2017; Scattoni-Silva et al., 2012; Zhang et al., 2018). Based on these factors, of course, it is very influential on athletes in producing achievements because it relates to the comfort of athletes in practicing and affects the concentration of athletes (Conant et al., 2008; Laborde et al., 2023).

Input evaluation is a basic or initial ability to support a program. Training ground, clothing and athlete equipment are part of the facilities and infrastructure that are not in accordance with the needs of athletes (Arovah & Putri, 2024; Capulis et al., 2014; Emad et al., 2020). Whereas facilities and infrastructure are supporting the success of sports coaching achievements for every effort to improve achievement in achieving the main goals of sports organizations (Daniel & Răzvan-Liviu, 2014; Drozdowska et al., 2011; Smith, 2014). The nutritional needs of athletes greatly affect athlete achievement. At FORKI Solok City, the nutritional needs of athletes are not sufficient. An athlete is expected to meet 15% of their total energy needs (di Fronso et al., 2024; Jemili et al., 2017; Ruiz & Hanin, 2011). The magnitude of the athletes' needs is certainly different, the consumption of athletes after being studied requires different proteins (Gomes et al., 2023; Pinto-Escalona et al., 2024). With a routine training schedule that increases the protein needs of athletes (Date et al., 2024; Malinga & Laing, 2021). Good sources of protein consumed include eggs, milk, cheese, meat, fish and various types of nuts. Based on the evaluation with the input component approach to the FORKI Solok City achievement coaching program, it turns out that it is still not fulfilled due to low funding so that the lack of good protein availability for athletes. The pattern and nutrition arrangements that must be consumed by FORKI Solok City athletes must be improved so that they can improve the achievements of FORKI Solok City athletes. The role of the coach in coaching is very influential on athlete achievement (Gough et al., 2021; Marttinen et al., 2022; Pedersen et al., 2022). The last education, achievement, experience, various training, creativity and social skills of the coach in providing motivators are still lacking. With the existence of standards in the selection or recruitment of athletes, of course, it is very influential on athlete achievement, because with these standards it is possible to get a coach with good abilities (O'Connor et al., 2024; Srivastava et al., 2024; Zhao et al., 2024). The higher the education of a coach, the better the way of thinking and social skills in providing motivators for athletes (Pate et al., 2023; Qi et al., 2024; Waters et al., 2022).

Process evaluation is a material used to implement a decision that will be taken, so that it can be seen the accuracy of the implementation of a program that has been determined (English et al., 2022; Zimmermann et al., 2024). Evaluation based on this component is coordination between agencies. The coordination that exists with other agencies is quite good (Lavorgna et al., 2023; Mendonça et al., 2022). With good coordination between agencies, assistance from the government is also obtained in

the form of APBN and APBD (Bruder et al., 2020; Sasaki & da Costa, 2021). Based on the aspects of this study, it is necessary to pay attention to coordination and seek coordination with other institutions, especially institutions engaged in karate outside West Sumatra. This aims to gain new knowledge for coaches and karate athletes. The welfare of FORKI Solok City athletes also needs attention, because based on the evaluation the level of welfare has not yet reached the good category. The low welfare of the athletes is caused by funds to meet the needs of athletes, coaches, and administrators of FORKI Kota Solok. The welfare of athletes greatly affects the achievements of athletes because the motivation of athletes greatly affects the performance of athletes in matches (Bernholt et al., 2024). If the welfare of athletes, coaches and administrators is low, then the enthusiasm and motivation they have is also low so that maintaining and improving achievement is also low (Clark et al., 2021; Yang et al., 2024). The process aspect in this study also discusses transportation. Transportation for coaches at FORKI Solok City is also not yet available, so it is still in sufficient condition. With the availability of a coach vehicle, it can make it easier to carry out his duties as a coach (Miralles-Muñoz et al., 2024; O'Connor et al., 2023). The evaluation results in this study indicate that the supporting personnel have been quite helpful in implementing the FORKI Solok City achievement improvement training program.

Product evaluation is an evaluation carried out to determine the level of achievement of FORKI Solok City's goals in a program that is implemented (Hurst et al., 2023; Liddelow et al., 2024; Reis et al., 2024). Athlete achievement is influenced by various factors, both internal and external factors (Kovács et al., 2024). Internal factors are factors that influence athletes who come from within the athlete himself with all the potential he has and his integration such as physical abilities, techniques, tactics, and mental abilities. While external factors are factors that come from outside the athlete or outside the potential possessed by the athlete, such as coaches, coaches, climate and weather, nutrition, facilities and infrastructure, organization, management, family and so on. The not so good achievements of athletes can be caused by the lack of integration of internal factors and external factors of FORKI Solok City athletes so that achievements at the international level are low (Hurst et al., 2020; Wynters et al., 2021). Internal factors and external factors must be integrated so that they become a collection of components derived from a combination and combination of these factors so that physical conditions and techniques can be applied to realize the components of tactics and strategies (Austin et al., 2024; Bang et al., 2024). Tactics and strategies in applying them require good mental abilities because they greatly affect the success of tactical action, both individually and in groups.

Outcome evaluation is an evaluation method by looking at the achievements of the program objectives such as the stability and ability of the athletes after participating in the program (Ball & Bennett, 2024). Based on the outcome of this study in order to find out how the achievement coaching program for FORKI Solok City athletes has an impact on the achievements obtained (Hsu et al., 2024; Krumm et al., 2023). Judging from the benefits of the program, the athletes who take part in the program have not felt the benefits enough to be seen from the achievements achieved by the athletes, especially at the international level (Sambol et al., 2024). So that it closes the possibility of athletes to get lucky absorption from the results of achievements achieved for their future.

Based on this research, it can be determined that the context component for the athlete achievement coaching program FORKI Solok City, especially in achieving the goal of producing outstanding athletes in karate sports. In this study, an evaluation and assessment of the effectiveness of the Karate athlete achievement coaching program FORKI Solok City with process and input components with the results tending to be less appropriate. This is due to a lack of coordination caused by poor communication between coaches, FORKI pengurus and athletes. In the implementation of the selection of athletes and coaches also tends to be less good because it has not gone according to what has been determined. The preparation of coaching programs in implementation also tends to be less appropriate because the use of facilities and infrastructure does not achieve the expected goals in accordance with the objectives of FORKI Kota Solok. The input component provided by FORKI Kota Solok will be utilized and used which will be seen in the process or implementation. The product component in evaluating this coaching program tends to be effective because it produces athletes who excel both at the regional and regional levels. The achievements of FORKI Solok City athletes at the national and international levels are still not effective due to the limited budget, the quality of coaches and facilities and infrastructure at FORKI Solok City.

CONCLUSIONS

This study concluded that the implementation of the athlete achievement coaching program FORKI Solok City in terms of the context component is quite effective, the input component is less effective, the process component is less effective, the product component is quite effective, the outcome component is less effective. The effectiveness of the implementation of the FORKI Solok City athlete achievement coaching program in terms of context, input, process, product and outcome is still less effective. In order for the goals of the FORKI Solok City achievement coaching program to be achieved effectively, it is necessary to pay attention to the related components. These components are the results of evaluation analysis based on context, input, process, product, and outcome. In each evaluation carried out in this study, it will produce interrelated efforts so that it can create an increase in achievement in coaching the achievements of FORKI Solok City athletes.

References

- 1) Arovah, N. I., & Putri, D. A. T. (2024). The acute effect of proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation recovery technique on fatigue in karate athletes. *Science & Sports*, 39(2), 206–213. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scispo.2023.02.004>
- 2) Austin, F., Wright, K. E., Jackson, B., Lin, A., Schweizer, K., & Furzer, B. J. (2024). A scoping review of trans and gender diverse children and adolescents' experiences of physical activity, sport, and exercise participation. *Mental Health and Physical Activity*, 26, 100576. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mhpa.2024.100576>
- 3) Ball, J., & Bennett, G. (2024). Bridging the gap: Connecting sport marketing theory and practice via an experiential sponsorship activation learning assignment. *Journal of Hospitality, Leisure, Sport & Tourism Education*, 34, 100475. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhlste.2023.100475>
- 4) Bang, H., Chang, M., & Kim, S. (2024). Team and individual sport participation, school belonging, and gender differences in adolescent depression. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 159, 107517. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2024.107517>

- 5) Bar-Eli, M., Lidor, R., Lath, F., & Schorer, J. (2024). The feudal glove of talent-selection decisions in sport –Strengthening the link between subjective and objective assessments. *Asian Journal of Sport and Exercise Psychology*, 4(1), 1–6.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajsep.2023.09.003>
- 6) Bernholt, D. L., Azar, F. M., & Lamplot, J. D. (2024). How to Get Involved with Sports Team Coverage (Local/National/Professional). *Clinics in Sports Medicine*.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csm.2024.03.004>
- 7) Brooke, L. E., Lin, A., Ntoumanis, N., & Gucciardi, D. F. (2020). The development of a sport-based life skills program for young people with first episode psychosis: An intervention mapping approach. *Mental Health and Physical Activity*, 19, 100330.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mhpa.2020.100330>
- 8) Bruder, A. M., Crossley, K. M., Mosler, A. B., Patterson, B., Haberfield, M., & Donaldson, A. (2020). Co-creation of a sport-specific anterior cruciate ligament injury risk reduction program for women: A concept mapping approach. *Journal of Science and Medicine in Sport*, 23(4), 353–360.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsams.2019.10.019>
- 9) Capulis, S., Dombrovskis, V., & Guseva, S. (2014). Karate-Do as a Means to Implement Humanistic Approach in Sports Education. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 112, 141–146. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.01.1148>
- 10) Clark, S. C., Sanborn, L., Brown, S. M., Trojan, J. D., & Mulcahey, M. K. (2021). Research Productivity of Orthopaedic Sports Medicine Fellowship Programs in the United States. *Arthroscopy, Sports Medicine, and Rehabilitation*, 3(4), e997–e1002.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asmr.2021.02.007>
- 11) Coleman, T., & Eys, M. (2024). The role of parents toward the group dynamics of youth sport teams. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 102676.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2024.102676>
- 12) Conant, K. D., Morgan, A. K., Muzykewicz, D., Clark, D. C., & Thiele, E. A. (2008). A karate program for improving self-concept and quality of life in childhood epilepsy: Results of a pilot study. *Epilepsy & Behavior*, 12(1), 61–65. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yebeh.2007.08.011>
- 13) Daniel, T. M., & Răzvan-Liviu, P. (2014). Correlation between Plantar Pressure and Striking Speed in Karate-do. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 117, 357–360.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.02.227>
- 14) Date, S., Munn, E., & Frey, G. C. (2024). Postural balance control interventions in autism spectrum disorder (ASD): A systematic review. *Gait & Posture*, 109, 170–182.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gaitpost.2024.01.034>
- 15) DeMartini, A. L., Kao, P. H., & McNiff-Villemaire, J. (2022). Small College Sport Management Students: A Population & Performance Case Study. *Journal of Hospitality, Leisure, Sport & Tourism Education*, 31, 100382. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhlste.2022.100382>
- 16) di Fronso, S., Robazza, C., Pompa, D., & Bertollo, M. (2024). Dreaming while awake: The beneficial effects of yoga Nidra on mental and physical recovery in two elite karate athletes. *Heliyon*, 10(1), e24180. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e24180>
- 17) Drozdowska, B., Münzer, U., Adamczyk, P., & Pluskiewicz, W. (2011). Skeletal Status Assessed by Quantitative Ultrasound at the Hand Phalanges in Karate Training Males. *Ultrasound in Medicine & Biology*, 37(2), 214–219.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultrasmedbio.2010.10.023>
- 18) Emad, B., Atef, O., Shams, Y., El-Kerdany, A., Shorim, N., Nabil, A., & Atia, A. (2020). iKarate: Improving Karate Kata. *Procedia Computer Science*, 170, 466–473.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2020.03.090>
- 19) English, M., Wallace, L., Evans, J., Diamond, S., & Caperchione, C. M. (2022). The impact of sport and physical activity programs on the mental health and social and emotional wellbeing of young Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Australians: A systematic review. *Preventive Medicine Reports*, 25, 101676. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmedr.2021.101676>

- 20) Fogaça, J. L., Quartirolí, A., & Wagstaff, C. R. D. (2024). Professional development of sport psychology practitioners: From systematic review to a model of development. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 70, 102550. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2023.102550>
- 21) Gomes, S. I. L., Chidiamassamba, S. B., Scott-Fordsmand, J. J., & Amorim, M. J. B. (2023). Environmental hazards of nanopesticides to non-target soil species - commercial nanoformulation versus its active substance (Karate Zeon® and lambda-cyhalothrin). *Science of The Total Environment*, 891, 164664. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.164664>
- 22) Gough, L. A., Duffell, T., & Eustace, S. J. (2021). The impact of student attendance on assessment specific performance in sport degree programs. *Journal of Hospitality, Leisure, Sport & Tourism Education*, 29, 100323. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhlste.2021.100323>
- 23) Hegyi, G., Maráczy, C., & Temesvári, E. (2022). Simulation of xenon transients in the VVER-1200 NPP using the KARATE code system. *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, 176, 109258. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2022.109258>
- 24) Hsu, J., Ling, D. I., Schneider, B. L., Boyle, C., Janosky, J., Pearle, A. D., Kinderknecht, J., & Marx, R. G. (2024). Independent data collectors decrease bias in the measurement of adherence to anterior cruciate ligament injury prevention programs. *Journal of ISAKOS*. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jisako.2024.02.004>
- 25) Hurst, P., King, A., Massey, K., Kavussanu, M., & Ring, C. (2023). A national anti-doping education programme reduces doping susceptibility in British athletes. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 69, 102512. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2023.102512>
- 26) Hurst, P., Ring, C., & Kavussanu, M. (2020). An evaluation of UK athletics' clean sport programme in preventing doping in junior elite athletes. *Performance Enhancement & Health*, 7(3), 100155. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.peh.2019.100155>
- 27) Indika, P. M., Kurniawan, R., Bahtra, R., & Yuniarti, E. (2023). The Effect of Administration of Honey on Maximal Physical Activity in Malondialdehyd (Mda) Levels of Male Mice (Mus musculus L.). *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Biology, Science and Education (IcoBioSE 2021)*, 171–180. https://doi.org/10.2991/978-94-6463-166-1_25
- 28) Jemili, H., Mejri, M. A., Sioud, R., Bouhleb, E., & Amri, M. (2017). Changes in muscle activity during karate guiaku-zuki-punch and kiza-mawashi-guiri-kick after specific training in elite athletes. *Science & Sports*, 32(2), 73–81. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scispo.2016.11.002>
- 29) Kovács, K., Oláh, Á. J., & Pusztai, G. (2024). The role of parental involvement in academic and sports achievement. *Heliyon*, 10(2), e24290. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e24290>
- 30) Krumm, C., Heinrich, N. W., & von Haaren-Mack, B. (2023). Affective reactions to real-life stressors and the role of physical activity in sports students – An Ambulatory Assessment study. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 69, 102503. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2023.102503>
- 31) Kuchar, A. L., Neff, K. D., & Mosewich, A. D. (2023). Resilience and Enhancement in Sport, Exercise, & Training (RESET): A brief self-compassion intervention with NCAA student-athletes. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 67, 102426. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2023.102426>
- 32) Laborde, M. R. R., Larramendy, M. L., & Soloneski, S. (2023). Cytotoxic and genotoxic profiles of the pyrethroid insecticide lambda-cyhalothrin and its microformulation Karate® in CHO-K1 cells. *Mutation Research/Genetic Toxicology and Environmental Mutagenesis*, 891, 503682. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mrgentox.2023.503682>
- 33) Lavorgna, T. R., Gupta, S., Maginnis, C., Saraf, S. M., Stamm, M. A., Wong, S. E., & Mulcahey, M. K. (2023). Persistent Lack of Female Orthopaedic Sports Medicine Fellows. *Arthroscopy, Sports Medicine, and Rehabilitation*, 5(4), 100725. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asmr.2023.02.016>

- 34) Liddelow, C., Schweickle, M. J., Sutcliffe, J. T., Swann, C., Keegan, R., Rice, S., Okely, A., & Vella, S. A. (2024). Defining the scope and content of mental health guidelines for community sport in Australia: A Delphi study. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 70, 102553. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2023.102553>
- 35) Malinga, L. N., & Laing, M. D. (2021). Efficacy of three biopesticides against cotton pests under field conditions in South Africa. *Crop Protection*, 145, 105578. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cropro.2021.105578>
- 36) Marttinen, R., Wilson, K., Fisher, K., Beitzel, M., & Fredrick, R. N. (2022). Process evaluation and challenges in collecting data from an after-school sports and literacy program in a diverse, low-income community. *Evaluation and Program Planning*, 91, 102052. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.evalprogplan.2022.102052>
- 37) Mendonça, L. D., Ley, C., Schuermans, J., Wezenbeek, E., IFSPT, & Witvrouw, E. (2022). How injury prevention programs are being structured and implemented worldwide: An international survey of sports physical therapists. *Physical Therapy in Sport*, 53, 143–150. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ptsp.2021.06.002>
- 38) Middleton, T. R. F., Petersen, B., Schinke, R. J., Kao, S. F., & Giffin, C. (2020). Community sport and physical activity programs as sites of integration: A meta-synthesis of qualitative research conducted with forced migrants. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 51, 101769. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2020.101769>
- 39) Miralles-Muñoz, F. A., de La Pinta-Zazo, C., Albero-Catalá, L., & Vizcaya-Moreno, M. F. (2024). The method of femoral tunnel drilling in anterior cruciate ligament reconstruction does not influence the return to sport rate. *Journal of Orthopaedics*, 56, 87–91. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jor.2024.05.017>
- 40) Noh, Y.-E., Zaki, F., & Danaee, M. (2024). The impact of religious–psychological factors on self-perceived sport performance among religious athletes in Malaysia. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 72, 102612. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2024.102612>
- 41) O'Connor, J., Grove, C., Jeanes, R., Lambert, K., & Bevan, N. (2023). An evaluation of a mental health literacy program for community sport leaders. *Mental Health & Prevention*, 29, 200259. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mhp.2023.200259>
- 42) O'Connor, J., Jeanes, R., Lambert, K., Bevan, N., Young, L., Powers, T., & Grove, C. (2024). The impact of a mental health literacy program on sporting club environment, member confidence and knowledge to support. *Mental Health & Prevention*, 33, 200326. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mhp.2024.200326>
- 43) Oulevey, M., Lavalley, D., Ojio, Y., & Kohtake, N. (2024). The design of a career transition psychological support program for retired Olympic athletes in Japan. *Asian Journal of Sport and Exercise Psychology*, 4(1), 7–10. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajsep.2024.01.001>
- 44) Pate, J. R., Hardin, R., Shapiro, D., & McKay, C. (2023). Inclusion, infusion, or confusion: Exploring how faculty address adaptive sport and recreation in the sport management classroom. *Journal of Hospitality, Leisure, Sport & Tourism Education*, 33, 100458. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhlste.2023.100458>
- 45) Pedersen, J. R., Hansen, S. H., Grindem, H., Jepsen, A. P., & Thorlund, J. B. (2022). Readiness for return to sport in non-surgically treated patients with anterior cruciate ligament injury following a public municipal rehabilitation program. *Physical Therapy in Sport*, 53, 7–13. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ptsp.2021.10.016>
- 46) Pinto-Escalona, T., Gobbi, E., Valenzuela, P. L., Bennett, S. J., Aschieri, P., Martin-Loeches, M., Paoli, A., & Martinez-de-Quel, O. (2024). Effects of a school-based karate intervention on academic achievement, psychosocial functioning, and physical fitness: A multi-country cluster randomized controlled trial. *Journal of Sport and Health Science*, 13(1), 90–98. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jshs.2021.10.006>

- 47) Qi, Y., Sajadi, S. M., Baghaei, S., Rezaei, R., & Li, W. (2024). Digital technologies in sports: Opportunities, challenges, and strategies for safeguarding athlete wellbeing and competitive integrity in the digital era. *Technology in Society*, 77, 102496. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2024.102496>
- 48) Quinzi, F., Bianchetti, A., Felici, F., & Sbriccoli, P. (2018). Higher torque and muscle fibre conduction velocity of the Biceps Brachii in karate practitioners during isokinetic contractions. *Journal of Electromyography and Kinesiology*, 40, 81–87. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jelekin.2018.04.005>
- 49) Raquel, G., Namba, E. L., Bonotto, D., Ribeiro Rosa, E. A., Trevilatto, P. C., Naval Machado, M. Â., Vianna-Lara, M. S., & Azevedo-Alanis, L. R. (2017). The use of a custom-made mouthguard stabilizes the electromyographic activity of the masticatory muscles among Karate-Dō athletes. *Journal of Bodywork and Movement Therapies*, 21(1), 109–116. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbmt.2016.05.007>
- 50) Reis, F. J. J., Alaiti, R. K., Vallio, C. S., & Hespanhol, L. (2024). Artificial intelligence and machine-learning approaches in sports: Concepts, applications, challenges, and future perspectives. *Brazilian Journal of Physical Therapy*, 101083. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bjpt.2024.101083>
- 51) Ruiz, M. C., & Hanin, Y. L. (2011). Perceived impact of anger on performance of skilled karate athletes. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 12(3), 242–249. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2011.01.005>
- 52) Sambol, S., Dadswell, K., & Hanlon, C. (2024). Beyond stereotypes: The role of exposure in reshaping Children’s biases towards women as coaches in sports. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 73, 102634. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2024.102634>
- 53) Sari, A. P., Bafirman, Rifki, M. S., Syafrianto, D., & Kurniawan, R. (2023). The impact of maumere gymnastics on blood pressure reduction in hypertensive patients: A promising non-pharmacological intervention. *Journal Sport Area*, 8(3), 328–339. [https://doi.org/10.25299/sportarea.2023.vol8\(3\).11727](https://doi.org/10.25299/sportarea.2023.vol8(3).11727)
- 54) Sari, A. P., Kurniawan, R., Indika, P. M., Wulan, T. S., Syafrianto, D., & Sari, D. N. (2023). Exploring the impact of aerobic gymnastics on reducing blood: with hypertension medications vs without hypertension medications. *Journal of Physical Education and Sport*, 23(12), 3253–3263. <https://doi.org/10.7752/jpes.2023.12372>
- 55) Sasaki, C. A. L., & da Costa, T. H. M. (2021). Micronutrient deficiency in the diets of para-athletes participating in a sports scholarship program. *Nutrition*, 81, 110992. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nut.2020.110992>
- 56) Scattone-Silva, R., Lessi, G. C., Lobato, D. F. M., & Serrão, F. V. (2012). Acceleration time, peak torque and time to peak torque in elite karate athletes. *Science & Sports*, 27(4), e31–e37. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scispo.2011.08.005>
- 57) Selviani, I., Welis, W., Syafrianto, D., Okilanda, A., Sari, A. P., Resmana, R., Kurniawan, R., & Crisari, S. (2024). Effectiveness of Use of Kinesiotapping in the Condition of Pain Plantar Fasciitis. *Community Practitioner*, 21(2), 170–175. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10731288>
- 58) Smith, E. N. (2014). *Chapter 5 - Practice Makes Perfect: Karate Forms and Organizational Memory* (E. N. B. T.-W. S. E. Smith (ed.); pp. 53–66). Butterworth-Heinemann. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-416557-1.00005-0>
- 59) Srivastava, S., Chakraborty, C., & Sarkar, M. K. (2024). Leveraging machine learning and dimensionality reduction for sports and exercise sentiment analysis. *Measurement: Sensors*, 33, 101182. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measen.2024.101182>
- 60) Tabaie, S. A., Nowell, J. A., Osadebey, E. N., Yastishak, J., & Murray, R. S. (2022). Adaptive Sport Participation in the Pediatric Population. *Journal of the Pediatric Orthopaedic Society of North America*, 4(3), 474. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.55275/JPOSNA-2022-0082>

- 61) Tinoco, A., Schneider, J., Haywood, S., & Matheson, E. L. (2023). "They are men, they will be looking even if you put on pants or a sweatshirt": Girl athletes' and coaches' experiences of body image in Mexico City sport settings. *Body Image*, 46, 73–83. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bodyim.2023.05.002>
- 62) Vences Brito, A. M., Rodrigues Ferreira, M. A., Cortes, N., Fernandes, O., & Pezarat-Correia, P. (2011). Kinematic and electromyographic analyses of a karate punch. *Journal of Electromyography and Kinesiology*, 21(6), 1023–1029. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jelekin.2011.09.007>
- 63) Waters, A. M., Sluis, R. A., Usher, W., Farrell, L. J., Donovan, C. L., Modecki, K. L., Zimmer-Gembeck, M. J., Castle, M., & Hinchey, J. (2022). Kick-starting youth wellbeing and access to mental health care: Efficacy of an integrated model of care within a junior sports development program. *Behaviour Research and Therapy*, 157, 104166. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brat.2022.104166>
- 64) Witte, K., Kropf, S., Darius, S., Emmermacher, P., & Böckelmann, I. (2016). Comparing the effectiveness of karate and fitness training on cognitive functioning in older adults—A randomized controlled trial. *Journal of Sport and Health Science*, 5(4), 484–490. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jshs.2015.09.006>
- 65) Wynters, R., Liddle, S. K., Swann, C., Schweickle, M. J., & Vella, S. A. (2021). Qualitative evaluation of a sports-based mental health literacy program for adolescent males. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 56, 101989. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2021.101989>
- 66) Yang, J., Meng, C., & Ling, L. (2024). Prediction and simulation of wearable sensor devices for sports injury prevention based on BP neural network. *Measurement: Sensors*, 33, 101104. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measen.2024.101104>
- 67) Yi, K., Luo, H., & Wei, L. (2024). From the pitch to personal growth: Investigating self-esteem as a mediator and parental support as a moderator in youth sports in China. *Heliyon*, 10(10), e31047. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e31047>
- 68) Zainal Abidin, N. E., Zulnaidi, H., Mamat, S., & Mafarja, N. (2023). Sport engagement model in Malaysia: Effect of cost and volunteerism. *Heliyon*, 9(11), e21198. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e21198>
- 69) Zhang, L., Brunnett, G., Petri, K., Danneberg, M., Masik, S., Bandow, N., & Witte, K. (2018). KarakTer: An autonomously interacting Karate Kumite character for VR-based training and research. *Computers & Graphics*, 72, 59–69. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cag.2018.01.008>
- 70) Zhao, J., Xiang, C., Kamalden, T. F. T., Dong, W., Luo, H., & Ismail, N. (2024). Differences and relationships between talent detection, identification, development and selection in sport: A systematic review. *Heliyon*, 10(6), e27543. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e27543>
- 71) Zimmermann, S., Dauter, J., & Gewalt, H. (2024). Promoting Sports and Wellness with Social Media Advertising – An Analysis of Different Marketing Channels. *Procedia Computer Science*, 231, 311–316. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2023.12.209>